

Participatory tools

TIMELINE AND LEARNING HISTORY

INTERACTIVE AND COLLECTIVE PROJECT WORK: MONITORING THE PARTICIPATORY PROCESS

How to monitor the participatory process?

As the project progresses, you need to check the motivation of the partners and the presence or not of tensions/conflicts to be resolved.

The process of evaluation throughout the project using participatory methods allows:

- Identify risks/problems and adapt
- Find solutions quickly
- Involve all partners
- Share/maintain an overview,
- Release tensions by exchanging and identifying problems that can be shared: catharsis effect.

How to solve it

Identify potential risks helps to anticipate conflicts and problems. To keep partners involved, the manager should know if they still have the necessary resources (time, budget, skills, etc.). An important point is to understand power relations and potential pre-project conflicts between partners, which can help you avoid conflicts or difficulties.

Regular contacts throughout the project help to stay involved. Another solution is to enable transparent communication. The consortium building the project can reserve time for self-reflection throughout the project and not only at the end. Offering the group regular time to reflect fosters trust and connection.

Taking diversity into account allows everyone's opinions and feelings to be considered. Everyone will have different feelings and constraints depending on their personalities, cultures, habits, etc.

Word of advice

Some conflicts may require a more detailed approach, so identify (as much as possible) the contextual elements in mind before organizing the collective work.

A session led by a facilitator from outside the project (neutral) can help to gain perspective.

You can find more details about project evaluation in LIAISON toolbox.

One example of a tool to facilitate this stage

Timeline and learning history – A collective travel to understand the past

Description of the tool

- **What:** Self-reflect on what has happened in the project so far (results, relationship, collaboration, etc.), take a step back and analyse the events to learn from them
- **How long:** about 2-3h
- **How many:** max 10 per group
- **What you'll need:** sticky notes of various sizes and colours, flip chart papers, markers

Steps:

Timeline

- Prepare a flip chart paper with an arrow representing the time from the beginning of the project (or the beginning of the building phase) to now.
- The participants identify individually, on sticky notes, three types of moments
 - Moments with a positive impact
 - Moments with a negative impact
 - Moments of flashing insights
- They place the sticky notes along the timeline
- Facilitate the exchange to be sure to understand every idea

Learning history

- Convert the timeline into a brief narrative story
- Divided the story into four to six scenes with a title for each
- Analyse each scene: What changes can be observed? What caused them? Which external factors were

important? And what did people in the network do to make it happen?

Testimony of the use

We used this tool in LIAISON in the middle of the project to self-reflect on how we have worked together since the project's launch. We split into three groups of about 10 participants to define our timeline.

It helped to:

- Rationally analyse events and to see things from a new perspective
- Understand tensions
- Identify successes and analyse them

The groups gathered people working on different project parts with various backgrounds and work habits. Everyone saw, understood, and lived the steps and actions from a different perspective.

Doing it together and therefore sharing the analysis helped us understand each other better and clarify and understand our common past better. In the end, we were more aware of the risks and the difficulties to avoid in the future.

Tips:

- Give clear instructions
- Prepare sticky notes of different sizes and colours
- Keep in mind that it could be a difficult exercise for partners who are new to the project

More tools: in Impact assessment handbook in LIAISON toolbox

